

A Survey on Optical Character Recognition for Text Extraction

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Abstract

In the modern world, practically everything is mechanised, and data is transmitted and stored digitally. There are, however, a number of circumstances in which the data is not digitised, and it may be necessary to extract text from them in order to save it in digitised form. The technique of text extraction utilising optical character recognition has been entirely revolutionised by the most recent technologies, such as text recognition software. Therefore, this article introduces the idea, describes the extraction procedure, and provides an overview of the newest methods, technologies, and ongoing research in the field. An overview of the technique will be provided to other researchers in the field by such a review.

Introduction

The process of computerising text or creating a digital copy of text from sources like handwritten papers, printed text, or from actual photographs is known as optical character recognition (OCR) [1]. The broad category of Digital Image Processing (DIP) encompasses it [2]. Digital image processing, or DIP, is the process of running digital pictures via a computer algorithm. DIP is an area that has applications in almost every other discipline, including the banking industry, robotics, and the healthcare sector for PET scans, among others, and it is still evolving. Pattern recognition, which encompasses computer-aided diagnosis, handwriting recognition, and picture identification, is one of its main uses.

The world's data is expanding at an exponential rate, necessitating the development of text recognition software. Since all of this data cannot be physically retained, it must be preserved digitally. Automatic Character Recognition, which makes use of OCR, is used as a result. These days, OCR frameworks are typically employed to extract text information from any artificial or computerised image.

OCR encourages checked archives to go beyond being only photo records, making them into fully searchable documents. As a result, it is frequently used for various objectives including information extraction. When creating a digital copy of a large report, users might use OCR to save having to retype it. OCR separates out relevant information, which is then entered regularly. It enables a machine to understand the information contained in an image as viewed when reading a written document and to store that information in a way that makes it easier to analyse later[3].

OCR has emerged as a crucial component of contemporary technology like text-to-speech software, barcode scanners, etc. Given that augmented reality, or AR, is based on object recognition, it is also utilised to support AR. OCRs may be used to identify not just text but also other objects. OCR was initially developed to aid the blind, but since then, technology has advanced significantly, making it simpler to develop a text-to-speech engine, as noted in [29].

Based on the kind of information, OCR frameworks may be characterized into 3:

1. Handwritten—Systems that only function with written text.
2. Machine printed: Those that exclusively use text that has been entered and then printed.
3. Specific kind - The language, typeface, and other variables all play a part in how the OCR functions. As a result, there are several OCR systems for certain languages, such as Urdu.

OCR was developed in 1914 to aid blind or differently abled persons, although it is now mostly used for text recognition. It made it possible for the blind to have written material read aloud to them by a machine. Additionally, as technology was not as

advanced and there was insufficient processing power in the 1950s, the development of OCR encountered various challenges including speed and accuracy [1]. Early optical character versions worked on one word at a time and required training on individual character representations.

Nowadays, several OCR tools are employed, including the Google Drive OCR, Tesseract, Transym, OmniPage, etc. While many of them require payment, some are free to use. [4] One of the most well-known and often employed OCR engines on the internet is called Tesseract. It operates via a four-step sequential procedure. Instead of accuracy, it emphasises covering a wide range of languages and typefaces. It is discovered that tesseract delivers greater accuracy on average than Transym OCR (another open-source OCR engine), although it is not always quicker. Programs/software utilise these engines to transform digital pictures into a format that may be used to modify them.

Modern wireless technologies enable devices to communicate data over networks rather than storing the complete OCR system there, where it would take a long time to process it and provide the findings to the device. One such web-based OCR converter that can operate as a whole system online is online OCR.

Related Work

In addition to the standard methods previously mentioned, a number of ideas put forth by different scholars in the area have been looked into and are included below:

A novel approach [11] with 7 phases was put forth to extract text from natural photos. The filtering procedure is first applied as preprocessing to enhance the image. The Thresholding method is used for lateral separation to separate the backdrop from the necessary material. The MSER (Maximally Stable External Region) is then found, and the unnecessary portion is removed. The stroke width variance algorithm next applies the stroke width computation, and finally, CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) is utilised to generate the characteristics needed for the OCR to recognise the letters to obtain the text.

Another [12] presented a neural network-based architecture that uses bidirectional long short-term memory (BLSTMB) to operate and enables word-level OCR. As compared to a standard OCR framework, it produces results that are over 20% better. One of the most prevalent causes of the mistake is that it employs a method that does not need segmentation. Additionally, when compared with the more frequently used OCR framework, it discovered a drop in character error of almost 9%.

[13] This method suggested separating content and non-content sections using a two-advance iterative Conditional Random Field (CRF) computation with a Belief Propagation obstacle, and then using OCR on the content component to produce the desired result. Two relational networks are employed in the scenario of numerous text lines to extract the various text lines, and the OCR certainty is used as a reference for locating text-containing regions.

[14] The Complete OCR Method for Historical Texts for Text Extraction from Historical Documents. It consists of three steps: the first includes binarization and improvement. In the following stage, line segments, words, and letters are distinguished using a high-level separation technique. The KNN integration theme is used to include the same group's symbols. Finally, in the third stage, the same prior classification approach is used to each image of the new document, while the recognition is based on the data extrapolated from the previous step. High throughput rates of up to 95.44% are the outcome.

Several processes are used in this program's text extraction from television. The hosting service is first utilised to process the data. The OCR method is then used to extract the text from the input data. The output from the preceding phase is then compared to the expected results, and before it is released, a determination is made as to whether it is right or not. This software may be used to evaluate TV sets in a real-world setting [15].

Identification of Vehicles via Number Plate Recognition: Security is one of the many fields where OCR is employed. You may use this technology to monitor traffic at the security entry. An image of the car is captured first, and then the number plate is extracted utilising portions of the image. The text is then extracted using OCR, and the information is then matched to the inventory data to identify the information for the car's owner. For security reasons, it creates a robust system with excellent dependability. [16] [17].

Several studies propose future directions for this field of study. For instance, according to [18], the accuracy of OCR may be impacted by presently increasing factors such Scan objectives, filtered picture quality, kind of printer used—whether ink-jet or laser—the type of paper used, phonetic complexity, the lopsided brightness, and watermarks. Therefore, effort may be done to

increase OCR's accuracy. An OCR framework looks at a variety of concerns [19], but Chinese and Arabic character recognition stands out since both languages have confusing frameworks, unbalanced text styles, and other challenges. When it comes to handwritten record photos, there are several problems, such as the likelihood of skewed, touching, or covered content lines. New methods like the Spiral Run Length Smearing Algorithm (SRLSA) have therefore been the subject of investigation. Additionally, as it isn't yet 100% accurate, the extracted text must be double-checked for mistakes, and for little amounts of text, it is simply not worth using since it is typically quicker to do manually than with contemporary OCR systems. There is no universal procedure that can be used to obtain the required outcome with great accuracy because every language and typeface is unique [22]. In this way, a lot of research is being done to increase the OCR framework's accuracy for a particular language or typeface, and even within the same language, several approaches might be used.

Script in Gurmukhi: [23] Gurmukhi content OCR has a number of problems, including covering characters, inconsistent writing styles, character comparability, the presence of background noise that cannot be avoided, and many types of mutilations. The feature extraction process and classifier are also different when different approaches are used for hand authored Gurmukhi text. With the use of several techniques, including feature extraction using zone density and BDD, SVM with the RBF bit as the classifier, and distinct results, the best accuracy of 95.04% was attained.

Script in Devanagari: [24] Devanagari script OCR employs algorithms for zoning feature extraction. Several techniques can be applied while using the zoning approach. Zoning performance significantly improved when the 4x4 grid was utilised, but when the 2x2, 8x8, or 16x16 grids were used, the performance was comparable to the value of the original feature. Thus, using a 4x4 grid size for Devanagari results in a noticeably higher output.

Script in Arabic: [25] Numerous letters may have varied forms based on the situation since it is written from right to left. Additionally, the semi-cursive nature and discontinuities make the OCR framework more problematic. The results obtained were 86% accurate, showing that the Generalised Hough Transformation may be utilised to increase character segmentation and font segmentation accuracy. Conversely, a success rate of up to 97% might be achieved using cursive.

Script in Bengali: [26] Bengali is the sixth most widely spoken language worldwide. Bengali characters don't contain upper- or lowercase letters like those in English, but they do feature a connecting portion called a "Matra" that makes identification more difficult. To organise various characters, Kohonen Neural Network (KNN), also known as Self-Organizing Map (SOM), is utilised. Comparing this to conventional approaches, recognition time is reduced by 33%.

Using the Rashi font Utilising fuzzy logic-based rules to support the algorithm and basing it on the factual data of the researched text style. In many fuzzy-based concepts, this novel technology combines letter measurements with connection coefficients, enabling the extraction of distorted letters that would not be recognised by existing approaches. The main focus is on Rashi textual criticisms of the calligraphically recorded Bible.

Indian document that is multilingual- [28] The different databases, including the textual and computer-generated records, are thoroughly examined. Around 99% accuracy was determined to be the optimum result. Additionally, techniques that support multilingual Indian report images with mixed Devanagari and Latin contents are suggested. The character's centre pixel is used to construct the first two components, while the neighbouring pixel information is used to compute the third component.

Figure Steps towards Recognition in OCR

The image acquisition:

The foundational step in OCR is image capture, which entails acquiring an advanced photo and altering it in a way that can be successfully processed later. Quantization of image and picture compression is included in this.

Preprocessing

Pre-processing is essential to achieving greater recognition rates since it strengthens OCR. The first step is binarization [6], which reduces a multi-tone image to black and white. The next steps, which increase the image's detail, are image enhancement processes [7].

Spatial image filtering methods are frequently employed to either make the image more rounded or the edges more pronounced. Point processing and mask processing are the next two divisions. While mask processing is performed on a collection of pixels, point processing is performed on each individual pixel.

Thresholding separates the data from an extraneous portion of the image. Usually, it is used with grayscale pictures. Global and local are the two components that make it up. Local approaches primarily apply to explicit apps and, more often than not, perform poorly on isolated applications, whereas global solutions tend to focus on a single value cutoff for the whole archive.

Noise reduction: Devices used to take photographs produce a variety of sounds, including those caused by photons, ambient illumination, internal circuitry, and so on. Even yet, contemporary technology makes it feasible to virtually completely eliminate noise when taking pictures.

Correction/detection – Natural photos are frequently rotated, which makes it difficult for an OCR framework to operate with them. Therefore, these photos need to be corrected before being processed further. There are many ways to do it, including the Hough transform.

Segmentation

As the name implies, segmentation is used to separate the necessary material from the background of the image.[8] It entails a number of steps:

1. **Page segmentation-** it is used to isolate content from the rest of the image, resulting in a text-only image. It can be portrayed into three general characterizations: top-down, base up, and a half and half strategies.
2. **Character segmentation-** it is seen as one of the chief strides in preprocessing especially in cursive contents where symbols are related together. Henceforth, there are various systems created for character division, and most by far of them are content unequivocal and may not work with various substances.
3. **Image size normalization-** The outcome from the character division stage gives isolated characters that make way to next process; in this way, the detached parts get standardized in a particular size tentatively relying upon the utilization later and the feature extraction or grouping techniques utilized, at that point highlights are removed from all characters with a steady size to give information consistently.
4. **Morphological processing-** Sometimes, few pixels may be evacuated creating openings to certain pieces of the pictures. It is like having a few gaps where a portion of the pixels was expelled during thresholding. Then again, the inverse can likewise be valid, it may overwrite separate items which result in difficulty to isolate characters; these strong articles take after masses and are difficult to decipher. The answer to these issues is Morphological Filtering. Helpful methods incorporate disintegration and expansion, opening and shutting, delineating, and diminishing and Skeletonization.

Feature extraction

In this step, each character is allocated a vector which at that point represents it. Its goal is to extract a group of features, that will increase the recognition for a small number of items and produce the same feature used in different instances of the same attribute.

1. Character zoning: A character is usually divided into zones of a fixed size. Typically, these predetermined or matrix sizes are 2x2, 4x4, and so forth. At that stage, the representations are created by segmenting the pixel or feature densities into different zones.
2. The projection histogram features use a highly precise method to count the number of pixels. Flat, vertical, and diagonal projection histograms are the three different types.
3. Distance profile features- These features count the pixels between the edge of the symbol and the merging box of the picture to calculate the distance. Any direction, including up, down, left, or right, may be taken with them.
4. Background directional distribution (BDD)—This technique is used to determine how much background is present in each front pixel. In order to determine the average grey matter value, a particular mask is employed in a variety of ways.
5. Combining different traits to increase accuracy. As shown in figure 2, more than one way may be utilised to achieve this.

Feature Vector	Included features
FV1	Zoning + profiles
FV2	BDD + zoning
FV3	BDD + histograms
FV4	Profiles + horizontal and vertical histograms(HVH)
FV5	BDD + HVH
FV6	BDD + Profiles
FV7	BDD + Diagonal (both) histograms

Figure 2 Combination of feature extraction methods

Classification

For classification, the characteristic vector that was obtained in the preceding phase is used. The information and several element vector should be compared in order to do the classification. [10] The element vector of information and the part vector of the data bank are analysed using a classifier. The application, setting up the set, and the quantity of free parameters all influence the classifier decision. There are many methods for categorization, however the three that are most frequently used are

1. Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN) classifier: This classifier uses the probability density function to categorise unknown patterns using a multi-layered feed-forward neural network.

Support Vector Machines (SVM) classifiers are supervised learning methods that may be used for regression or classification. It takes a variety of input and makes a prediction on how to divide them into the top two categories. An SVM classifier is trained using a collection of coaching data, and a model is created entirely based on this to categorise test statistics.

The third classifier is the K-Nearest Neighbour (K-NN) classifier, which applies a model-based instruction to an unknown pattern that is known for a specific distance or other comparable activity. The object is divided based on the votes of its neighbours. It makes advantage of the spatial correlation of the distance function since it only considers a nearby item up to a particular degree.

Post-Processing

It is the last advance after the arrangement. As the outcomes are not 100% right, particularly for complex dialects, Post handling procedures can be performed to improve the precision of OCR frameworks. These procedures use characteristic language

preparing, geometric, and etymological setting to address blunders in OCR results. Postprocessor ought not to take a lot of time and cause new blunders.

Conclusion

Applications for optical character recognition are numerous. It is used to extract text from old books, scripts, and other materials as well as from photographs. There is continuous research in this field to increase the range of text that can be read by a single OCR system and enhance the accuracy of the retrieved text. Since it first emerged, researchers have had to overcome a number of difficulties. Some of them, like the early OCR systems' poor speed, have been resolved, while others, like obtaining 100% accuracy and a restricted range for a single OCR, remain unresolved. As a result, even though this sector is seeing a tremendous quantity of investigation, there is still plenty of room for much more. Future research may yield new methods or algorithms that increase precision and contribute to the development of an OCR system that can process any type of dataset, independent of language, font, or other factors. It may also be utilised for a lot more applications with the aid of other sectors like artificial intelligence and augmented reality, and its potential are virtually limitless.

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